

BURDEN OF WORK-RELATED MUSCULOSKELETAL DISORDERS AMONG SUGAR INDUSTRY WORKERS IN KHYBER PAKHTUNKHWA: FREQUENCY AND RISK PATTERNS

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Abstract

Background: Work-related musculoskeletal disorders are a major cause of occupational illness worldwide, leading to disability, absenteeism, and reduced productivity. Evidence from Pakistan's sugar industry is lacking despite its large workforce and physically demanding environment. The purpose of this study was to determine the frequency and risk patterns of Work-related musculoskeletal disorders among sugar industry workers in Mardan, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.

Material & Methods: An analytical cross-sectional study was conducted recruiting 313 workers of Mardan Sugar Mill, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. Participants aged 15-60 years with at least three months of employment and minimum four working hours per day were included. Data were collected using a modified Standardized Nordic Musculoskeletal Questionnaire. Frequencies, percentages and associations between Work-related musculoskeletal disorders and risk factors were analyzed through SPSS V.27 using the chi-square test.

Results: Overall, 70.0% of participants reported Work-related musculoskeletal disorders. The lower back was the most affected site (24.9%), followed by knees (11.5%), shoulders (10.4%), and neck (9.0%). Work-related musculoskeletal disorders were more common among females (80.6%) than males (68.8%). Younger workers (15-29 years) showed higher prevalence compared to older groups. Significant associations were found between Work-related musculoskeletal disorders and high Body Mass Index, working more than eight hours daily, and longer work experience ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: Work-related musculoskeletal disorders are highly prevalent among sugar industry workers in Pakistan, with lower back and knee disorders being most

common. Preventive ergonomic interventions, workload adjustments, and worker education are urgently needed. Occupational health policies and surveillance systems should be prioritized to reduce this burden and protect industrial workers' well-being.

INTRODUCTION

Work-related musculoskeletal disorders (WRMSDs) are among the most prevalent occupational health problems worldwide. The World Health Organization (WHO) defines musculoskeletal disorders as health problems of the locomotor apparatus and connective tissues, including muscles, tendons, bones, cartilage, ligaments, and nerves, ranging from mild discomfort to permanent disability (1). Among industrial workers, these conditions are often termed “diseases of workers” because they result from repetitive physical strain, heavy lifting, awkward postures, and long working hours(2). WRMSDs have a major impact on workers' quality of life, causing absenteeism, functional limitations, and disability, which directly affect socioeconomic status(3, 4)

Globally, WRMSDs account for a large proportion of occupational disorders. The International Labor Organization estimates that around 160 million work-related disorders occur annually, with musculoskeletal (MSK) conditions playing a prominent role(5). In the United States, musculoskeletal disorders of the upper extremities represent more than 60% of newly reported occupational illnesses(6, 7). In Britain, they are considered the largest group of work-related health problems, accounting for nearly 39% of all occupational illnesses in 2016–2017(8). Similarly, prevalence rates are alarmingly high across the globe in the construction workers, with studies reporting 24.3% in Japan(9), 60.1% in Sweden(10), 10.98% in the United States(7), and 23.4% in China(11). In Korea, WRMSDs represent almost 70% of compensated occupational disorders in recent years(12).

Evidences from industrial settings consistently highlights the heavy burden of WRMSDs. A study among semiconductor assembly workers in Malaysia reported musculoskeletal symptoms in 57.8% of participants, with the back being the most affected site, followed by the lower limbs and

shoulders(13). Research in Korea among heavy industrial workers showed that shoulder injuries (38%) and back sprains and spasms (25%) were the most common MSK conditions followed by the leg (12%), elbow/lower arm (10%), wrist/hand (7%), and neck (6%) (12). In Brazil, MSK pain in the upper extremities was reported by more than half of manufacturing company workers, while similar findings were observed among construction workers in India, where poor equipment design, awkward postures, and unsafe working environments contributed to high rates of discomfort (14, 15). In Europe, studies from shipyard, mining, and automotive industries consistently demonstrate that back pain, shoulder pain, and upper limb disorders are the most frequent problems among workers exposed to heavy and repetitive tasks (16, 17).

The etiology of WRMSDs is multifactorial. Mechanical exposures such as repetitive strain, awkward or static postures, and vibration are well-known contributors (18). Psychosocial factors, including job monotony, work-related stress, and low job satisfaction, further increase susceptibility. Individual characteristics also play a role: younger workers performing repetitive work are at higher risk, while overweight individuals face increased biomechanical strain (19). Symptoms may include pain, stiffness, numbness, swelling, tingling, and weakness, commonly affecting the lower back, neck, shoulders, knees, and upper limbs (20, 21). Classification is often based on severity, ranging from mild discomfort during work to severe persistent pain and functional limitation(22).

In Pakistan, occupational health research is limited, and WRMSDs have not been widely studied in industrial populations. The sugar industry is one of the most labor-intensive sectors of the country, where workers are routinely exposed to repetitive bending, heavy lifting, and prolonged hours in awkward postures. Despite this, no published epidemiological data are

available on the burden of WRMSDs among sugar mill workers in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP). This gap is important because the sugar industry contributes significantly to the economy and employs a large workforce. Without preventive strategies, ergonomic interventions, or awareness programs, these workers remain at risk of chronic musculoskeletal problems, which can reduce productivity and increase healthcare costs. The primary objective of this study was to determine the frequency of work-related musculoskeletal disorders among industrial workers in Mardan Sugar Mill, Mardan, KP. While the secondary purposes include; establishing workers' awareness of work-related musculoskeletal disorders, identifying the most commonly affected body regions, determining the prevalence of WRMSDs across demographic and occupational risk factors (age, gender, BMI, working hours, work experience, and assessing the impact of WRMSDs on work capacity and treatment outcomes.

Given the rising global burden of musculoskeletal disorders and the lack of evidence from Pakistan's sugar industry, this study was conducted to determine the frequency and risk patterns of WRMSDs among workers in Mardan Sugar Mill, KP. The findings aim to establish baseline data to inform occupational health policy and guide preventive and rehabilitative measures for worker well-being.

Material & Methods

Study setting and participants inclusion:

An analytical cross-sectional study was carried out during (March 2025 - August 2025) at Mardan Sugar Mill, District Mardan, KP, Pakistan. The target population included all registered employees who fulfilled the inclusion criteria. Eligible participants were male and female workers aged 15-60 years, employed for at least three months, and working a minimum of four hours per day. Workers who were temporary, daily-wage or contract, under 15 or above 60 years, had recent history of musculoskeletal surgery within 6 months, had a history of pre-existing MSK condition diagnosed before or during employment in the last 6 months or employed for less than three months were excluded.

Sample Size, Sampling and Data Analysis

The sample size was calculated using the formula for infinite population, assuming a 95% confidence level and 5% margin of error. The minimum required size was 285. To account for potential non-response, an additional 10% was included, giving a final sample of 313 workers. Participants were selected through convenience sampling across different sectors of the mill. Data were obtained using a pre-tested, modified version of the Standardized Nordic Musculoskeletal Questionnaire (NMQ), a validated instrument for assessing MSK symptoms in occupational health research (23, 24). The questionnaire comprised two sections: demographic variables (age, sex, marital status, education, years of experience, working hours, and BMI) and musculoskeletal complaints (affected body regions, pain severity, and functional limitations). Questionnaires were distributed in paper format and explained in simple language. Face-to-face collection minimized errors and ensured completeness. Responses were entered into SPSS v.27 for analysis. Descriptive statistics (frequencies and percentages) were calculated for all demographic and outcome variables. Associations between WRMSDs and independent factors such as age, sex, BMI, marital status, education, work experience, and working hours were evaluated by applying chi-square test.

Ethical considerations:

Ethical approval (Ref # SIRMS/REC/Letter 16th /00016B) was obtained from the Institutional Research Committee (IRB) of Swat Institute of Rehabilitation and Medical Sciences, Swat, KP. Written permission was also granted by the sugar mill administration. Well-understood verbal consent was obtained from all participants after explaining the objectives and procedures of the study. Participation was voluntary, anonymity was maintained, and confidentiality of data was assured. The study adhered to ethical principles outlined by the Pakistan Health Research Council (PHRC) and the WHO for research involving human participants.

Results

A total of 313 workers from Mardan Sugar Mill, KP participated in the study. The demographic and occupational characteristics of participants are summarized in Table 1. The mean age was 33.7 years (SD ±9.4), with most workers (62.62%) belonging to the 15–29 years age group. The majority were male (88.5%), married (79.6%), and

had a normal body mass index (56.5%) (Fig. 1). Nearly half (46.6%) reported working more than eight hours per day, and 42.2% had 10–20 years of industry experience.

Variable	Categories	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age group (years)	15–29	196	62.6%
	30–44	55	17.6%
	45–60	62	19.8%
Gender	Male	277	88.5%
	Female	36	11.5%
Marital status	Married	249	79.6%
	Unmarried	64	20.4%
Body Mass Index	Underweight	37	11.8%
	Normal	177	56.5%
	Overweight	66	21.1%
	Obese	33	10.5%
Working hours/day	≤8 hours	167	53.4%
	>8 hours	146	46.6%
Experience (years)	<10 years	119	38.0%
	10–20 years	132	42.2%
	>20 years	62	19.8%

Note: Values are expressed as frequency and percentage of total participants

Table 1 Demographic and occupational characteristics of participants (N = 313)

Figure 1 Prevalence of Work-Related Musculoskeletal Disorders

Out of 313 participants, 219 reported experiencing WRMSDs in at least one body region during the last 12 months, yielding an overall prevalence of 70.0%. The most frequently affected region was the lower back (24.9%), followed by knees (11.5%), shoulders (10.4%), and neck

(9.0%). Upper back symptoms were reported by 8.0% of workers, whereas wrist/hand (3.2%), elbow (1.9%), and hip/thigh (1.0%) symptoms were less common. No participant reported ankle/foot disorders (Fig.2).

Figure 2 Prevalence of Work-related Musculoskeletal Disorders by body region

Note: Multiple responses possible as participants reported more than one affected body region

Association of WRMSDs with Demographic Factors

The occurrence of WRMSDs varied significantly across demographic groups (Table 2). Females were disproportionately affected, with 80.6% reporting WRMSDs compared to 68.8% of males, and this difference was statistically significant ($p = 0.04$). Age also showed a significant association ($p = 0.03$). Younger workers (15–29 years) had the

highest prevalence (62.8%), followed by 65.4% in the 30–44 years group, while only 24.6% of the 45–60 years group reported symptoms. With respect to BMI, prevalence was highest in workers with over-weight BMI (63.3%), compared to obese (62.1%), normal (57.6%), and underweight (54.1%), with the differences reaching statistical significance ($p = 0.01$).

Variable	Categories	WRMSD's Present n (%)	WRMSD Absent n (%)	Total	P-value
Gender	Male	190 (68.8%)	87 (31.2%)	277	0.04*
	Female	29 (80.6%)	7 (19.4%)	36	
Age (years)	15–29	137 (62.8%)	81 (37.2%)	218	0.03*
	30–44	68 (65.4%)	36 (34.6%)	104	
	45–60	14 (24.6%)	43 (75.4%)	57	
BMI	Normal	19 (57.6%)	14 (42.4%)	33	0.01*
	Underweight	20 (54.1%)	17 (45.9%)	37	
	Overweight	112 (63.3%)	65 (36.7%)	177	
	Obese	41 (62.1%)	25 (37.9%)	66	

Table 2 Association of WRMSDs with occupational factors (N=313)

Association with Occupational Factors

Occupational variables were also significantly related to musculoskeletal complaints (Table 3). Those working ≤ 8 hours per day had a prevalence of 64.7%, compared to 76.0% in those working > 8 hours, and this difference was statistically significant ($p = 0.02$). Similarly, prevalence

increased with job tenure: 62.2% in workers with < 10 years of experience, 73.5% in those with 10–20 years, and 77.4% in those with > 20 years of experience, with a significant association observed ($p = 0.04$).

Variable	Categories	WRMSD's Present n (%)	WRMSD Absent n (%)	Total	P-value
Working hours/day	≤ 8 hours	108 (64.7%)	59 (35.3%)	167	0.02*
	> 8 hours	111 (76.0%)	35 (24.0%)	146	
Experience (in years)	< 10 years	74 (62.2%)	45 (37.8%)	119	0.04*
	10–20 years	97 (73.5%)	35 (26.5%)	132	
	> 20 years	48 (77.4%)	14 (22.6%)	62	

Values are frequencies and percentages. * $p < 0.05$ indicates statistical significance (chi-square test)

Table 3 Association of WRMSDs with occupational factors (N=313)

Discussion

This study found a high prevalence of WRMSDs among sugar industry workers in Mardan, with 70% of participants reporting symptoms in at least one body region. The most affected sites were the lower back (24.9%), knees (11.5%), shoulders (10.4%), and neck (9.0%). These findings align with global evidence that highlights the back and lower limbs as the most commonly affected regions in industrial workers. The overall prevalence of 70% in this study is comparable to international estimates ranging between 60% and 90% in different industrial populations (25-28). However, it appears higher than some regional studies in South Asia, where prevalence in textile and manufacturing workers ranged from 40% to 60%(14). This suggests that sugar industry tasks may impose particularly high ergonomic strain, possibly due to manual handling, repetitive bending, and lack of ergonomic infrastructure. The predominance of lower back complaints in this study is consistent with reports from Pakistan, Malaysia and Korea, where repetitive bending and awkward lifting postures were identified as major contributors(13, 29, 30). Similarly, Brazilian and Indian studies in the metal and construction industries also reported high rates of back and lower limb symptoms, linking them to physically demanding and ergonomically unsafe work environments (14, 15). The burden of knee and

shoulder problems observed here is also in line with European studies from automotive, shipyard and mining industries, where repetitive heavy lifting and constrained postures were key risk factors (10, 17).

Gender differences were pronounced, with females reporting higher prevalence than males, consistent with earlier studies suggesting greater vulnerability due to both biological and occupational role factors (31). Gender differences were notable, with females reporting higher prevalence (80.6%) than males (68.8%). This supports findings from other occupational health studies, which suggest that biological factors, combined with differences in task allocation, contribute to greater vulnerability among women(32-34). Younger workers (15–29 years) also showed higher prevalence compared to older groups. This is in contrast to some studies where cumulative exposure among older workers increased risk, but it may reflect differences in physical workload distribution, with younger employees often assigned more physically demanding tasks(10, 35).

Workers with high BMI reported higher prevalence of WRMSDs than those who were normal, underweight, or obese. This finding aligns with previous reports linking overweight and obesity with higher musculoskeletal strain(36). Occupational factors were strongly associated with WRMSDs. Those working longer than eight hours

daily had significantly higher prevalence (76.0%) compared to those working shorter shifts. Similar associations between extended working hours and musculoskeletal pain have been reported in studies from Asia and Europe(3, 37, 38). Likewise, increasing years of work experience were positively associated with WRMSDs, consistent with cumulative exposure models of occupational health risk(38).

The novelty of this study is in its focus on sugar industry workers in Pakistan, a group previously unstudied despite their substantial contribution to the labor force. The findings provide baseline data for occupational health stakeholders in KP. Importantly, they highlight the urgent need for ergonomic interventions such as redesigning workstations, introducing mechanical aids for load handling, scheduling regular breaks, and educating workers about safe postures. Despite these limitations, the results underscore the need for occupational health policies in Pakistan's sugar industry. Employers and policymakers should prioritize ergonomic modifications, worker training, and health surveillance programs to reduce the burden of WRMSDs. Preventive physiotherapy interventions and workplace-based awareness campaigns may help mitigate risks and improve long-term productivity. Future research should include longitudinal studies to explore causal relationships and interventional trials to assess ergonomic solutions.

Strengths and limitations

A major strength of this study is the relatively large sample size and focus on an under-researched industrial sector in Pakistan. The use of a validated tool (NMQ) enhances reliability and comparability with international studies. However, certain limitations must be noted. The cross-sectional design prevents establishing causality. Convenience sampling may limit generalizability to all sugar industry workers. Self-reported symptoms could also introduce recall bias or underreporting. Finally, the absence of clinical

diagnosis may underestimate severity or misclassify other causes of musculoskeletal pain.

Conclusion

This study revealed a high burden of WRMSDs among sugar industry workers in Mardan, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, with 70% reporting symptoms. The lower back, knees, shoulders, and neck were the most commonly affected regions. WRMSDs were significantly associated with female gender, younger age, higher BMI, long working hours, and increased job tenure. As the first study to document the burden of WRMSDs among sugar industry workers in Pakistan, these findings provide critical baseline evidence. Ergonomic interventions such as redesigning workstations, mechanical aids for lifting, and reducing repetitive postures could help reduce strain. Regular rest breaks and shift adjustments should be incorporated into work schedules. Worker training on proper body mechanics and awareness of early musculoskeletal symptoms may also play a critical role. At the policy level, the sugar industry should integrate occupational health surveillance programs and adopt national-level guidelines for workplace ergonomics. Collaboration between physiotherapists, occupational health experts, and industry managers is essential to safeguard worker health and productivity.

Recommendations for future studies:

Longitudinal studies should be adopted to explore causal relationships between workplace exposures and WRMSDs. Implement interventional studies testing ergonomic solutions and physiotherapy-led preventive programs, as well as researches should be extended to other industries in Pakistan to compare risk patterns and generalize findings across different regions and geography. By addressing these areas, both industry and healthcare policymakers can reduce the occupational burden of MSK disorders and improve the quality of life of industrial workers.

CRedit authorship contribution statement:

CRedit	Author's Contribution
Conceptualization	Author no. 1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8
Methodology	Author no. 1,4,5,6,7
Data curation	Author no. 3,4,5,8
Writing - original draft	Author no. 1,2,3,6,7
Writing - review & editing	Author no. 1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8

Ethical Approval: Ethical Approval was obtained from the IRB of parent institute SIRMS, Swat, KP, Pakistan with the reference number "Ref # SIRMS/REC//Letter16th/000016B".

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